

An Open Source, Parallel, and Distributed Web-Based Probabilistic Risk Assessment Platform to Support Real Time Nuclear Power Plant Risk-Informed Operational Decisions

Milestone Report

Task 4: Applications to Single Hazard Real World PRA Models

Egemen M. Aras, Arjun Earthperson, Hasibul H. Rasheeq, S. Ted Wood (INL), Jordan T. Boyce (INL), Mihai A. Diaconeasa

November 1, 2024

Executive Summary

This milestone report is a cornerstone in making an actual PRA model publicly available in various formats. Having this model is crucial for performance measurement and verification of results across different tools. Additionally, being able to examine different modeling approaches may help reduce subjectivity in the modeling process.

The foundation for building a multi-hazard PRA model has also been established. Our focus is not only on modeling the system but also on ensuring the exact solution of the logic.

Acknowledgments

This research is funded by the Department of Energy's (DOE) Nuclear Energy University Program (NEUP) under project number 21-24004. Additionally, the SAPH SOLVE analysis and results would not have been possible without collaboration with the SAPHIRE development team at Idaho National Laboratory. Lastly, invaluable support and feedback from our research group, the Probabilistic Risk Assessment Group (PRAG), have been instrumental in achieving this outcome.

Disclaimer

The content of this report is largely a combination of various project outcomes, including conference papers, a master's thesis, and a Ph.D. dissertation.

Outcomes of the Project

The project contributes to the research environment in various ways, and the outcomes are listed below for reference. In addition to the listed outcomes, two journal papers are ready for submission, and one report covering the SAPHIRE post-processing engine is under review. Furthermore, North Carolina State University and Idaho National Laboratory have established a highly efficient collaborative environment.

1.1 Conference Papers

1. Benchmark Study of XFTA and SCRAM Fault Tree Solvers Using Synthetically Generated Fault Tree Models [1]
2. Methodology and Demonstration for Performance Analysis of a Probabilistic Risk Assessment Quantification Engine: SCRAM [2]
3. Method of Developing a SCRAM Parallel Engine for Efficient Quantification of Probabilistic Risk Assessment Models [3]
4. Introducing OpenPRA: A Web-Based Framework for Collaborative Probabilistic Risk Assessment [4]
5. Evaluating PRA Tools for Accurate and Efficient Quantifications: A Follow-up Benchmarking Study Including FTREX [5]
6. Introducing OpenPRA's Quantification Engine: Exploring Capabilities, Recognizing Limitations, and Charting the Path to Enhancement [6]
7. Enhancing the SAPHIRE Solve Engine: Initial Progress and Efforts [7]
8. Advancing SAPHIRE: Transitioning from Legacy to State-of-Art Excellence [8]
9. Towards a Deep-Learning Based Heuristic for Optimal Variable Ordering in Binary Decision Diagrams to Support Fault Tree Analysis [9]

1.2 Journal Papers

1. A Critical Look at the Need for Performing Multi-Hazard Probabilistic Risk Assessment for Nuclear Power Plants [10]

1.3 Reports

1. Refining Processing Engines from SAPHIRE: Initialization of Fault Tree/Event Tree Solver [11]

1.4 Master's Thesis

1. Benchmarking Study of Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools Using Synthetically Generated Fault Tree Models: SAPHSOLVE, XFTA, and SCRAM [12]

1.5 Ph.D. Dissertation

1. Enhancement Methodology for Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools through Optimization and Parallel Computing [13]

Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	2
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS.....	3
DISCLAIMER.....	4
OUTCOMES OF THE PROJECT.....	5
1.1 Conference Papers.....	5
1.2 Journal Papers	5
1.3 Reports	5
1.4 Master's Thesis.....	6
1.5 Ph.D. Dissertation.....	6
CONTENTS	7
LIST OF FIGURES	8
LIST OF TABLES.....	9
ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS	10
1 APPLICATIONS TO REAL WORLD PROBABILISTIC RISK ASSESSMENT MODELS	11
1.1 Overview of Report.....	11
1.2 Generic PWR Model with Single Hazard	11
1.2.1 Model Quantification Using SAPHIRE	13
1.2.2 Model Conversion from SAPHIRE to OpenPSA.....	16
1.2.3 Current Model Exchange Methodology	16
1.2.4 Method of Model Exchange Between PRA Tools.....	17
1.3 Generic PWR Model with Multi-Hazard.....	23
1.4 Conclusion and Alignment to Project Goals.....	22
2 REFERENCES.....	23

List of Figures

Figure 1. Actual PRA model solving and converting methodology overview.	12
Figure 2. Pseudocode for model quantification using SAPHIRE	14
Figure 3. Gas-leak event tree.	18
Figure 4. Gas-detection system fault tree.	19
Figure 5. Isolation valve A fault tree.	19
Figure 6. Isolation valve B fault tree.	20
Figure 7. Blowdown valve fault tree.	20
Figure 8. Engine-Level Model Exchange Framework.	21
Figure 9. Demonstration of Engine-Level Model Exchange Framework.	21

List of Tables

Table 1. Quantification results of generic PWR model.	14
Table 2. Demo model results comparison for SCRAM and SAPHSOLVE.	22

Acronyms and Abbreviations

BWR	Boling Water Reactor
CSN	Spanish Regulatory Body
GUI	Graphical User Interface
INL	Idaho National Laboratory
ISLOCA	Interfacing Systems LOCA
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LOCA	Loss of Cooling Accident
MAR-D	Models and Results Database
MEF	Model Exchange Framework
NRC	Nuclear Regulatory Commission
PC	Personal Computer
PRA	Probabilistic Risk Assessment
PWR	Pressurized Water Reactor
SARA	System Analysis and Risk Assessment
SETS	Set Equation Transformation Systems
SPAR	Standardized Plant Analysis Risk
TEMAC	Top Event Matrices Analysis Code
US	United States
XML	Extensible Markup Language

1 Applications to Real World Probabilistic Risk Assessment Models

1.1 Overview of Report

This report marks a significant milestone in the overall project. As a reminder, the project consists of five main tasks, which are outlined below. This milestone report presents the outcomes of the fourth task:

- Task 1: Literature review, benchmarking, and profiling of current PRA tools
- Task 2: Design and implementation
- Task 3: Testing and benchmarking for serial and parallel improvements
- Task 4: Application to real world PRA models
- Task 5: Verification and documentation

The remainder of the report is as follows: Section 1.2 delves into the generic PWR model, along with other available PRA models, and introduces the model converter, which is essential for providing PRA models in various formats for different quantification engines. Section **Error! Reference source not found.** discusses ongoing efforts in the development of a multi-hazard PRA model. Section 1.3 concludes the report with a summary of key findings.

1.2 Generic PWR Model with Single Hazard

During the improvement process of a Probabilistic Risk Assessment (PRA) tool, various models were used, including synthetic fault tree models [14] and publicly available real-life fault tree models [15]. While these models are extremely valuable for improvement purposes, it is essential to demonstrate our findings using a real-world PRA model.

Generally, actual PRA models are not accessible to the research community due to the confidentiality of the information they contain. To address this, we conducted a literature review of publicly available models and found generic models that do not represent specific plants but rather a generic plant design.

Since 1995, Idaho National Laboratory (INL) has developed Standardized Plant Analysis Risk (SPAR) models for the United States (US) Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC) to provide critical risk-informed input to the regulatory process [16]. These models are only available to the NRC. As of now, the SAPHIRE official webpage reports that 91 SPAR models have been developed and are continuously being improved [17].

In response to this gap, the research community has developed its own generic models. For example, researchers at ETH developed generic pressurized water reactor (PWR) and boiling water reactor (BWR) models covering internal events [18]. Additionally, the Spanish Regulatory Body (CSN), in collaboration with the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), created its own generic standardized model (SPAR-CSN) for 3-loop PWR-WEC designs [19]. In the US, the NRC addressed this need by distributing a generic PWR model developed by INL [20], which is the model we will be using for demonstration.

The generic PWR model is available as a SAPHIRE model, accompanied by a report detailing the foundations of the modeling phenomena and referencing failure data. The current version of the SAPHIRE model is V1.2; however, the documented model information corresponds to V1.0. This model is continuously evolving, with researchers and PRA practitioners actively working to improve it.

At present, the model considers various initiating events, including seismic activity, internal flooding, internal fires, hurricanes, high winds, ISLOCA (Interfacing Systems LOCA), upset conditions leading to transients, large break LOCA, loss of CCW (Component Cooling Water), loss of DC bus, loss of feedwater, loss of offsite power, large steam line breaks, medium break LOCA, steam generator tube ruptures, small LOCA, tornadoes, and excessive LOCA.

Version 1.0 of the model includes 56 event trees linked with 140 fault trees.

The process of leveraging the existing generic PWR model is shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Actual PRA model solving and converting methodology overview.

The PRA model logic and data are available, and the model is quantified using SAPHIRE to obtain the results. SAPHIRE can export models in various formats, such as MAR-D [21] or JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) [22]. The JSON format is preferred because it allows the model to be solved using only SAPHIRE's quantification engine, SAPHISOLVE, without requiring SAPHIRE's graphical user interface. This flexibility enables solving sub-models independently of the full interface.

The exported JSON models are then converted into the Open-PSA [23] Extensible Markup Language (XML) format. The next step is to solve the model using our in-house engine under development, SCRAM. Afterward, the results are compared in terms of the number of cut sets and overall probability. If any discrepancies are found, each step is revisited, starting from model export through SCRAM solving. All exported [24] models are stored in the repository.

Details on model quantification using SAPHIRE and the conversion from SAPHIRE JSON to Open-PSA XML are provided in following sub-sections.

1.2.1 Model Quantification Using SAPHIRE

Users can utilize an external solver through the SAPHIRE graphical user interface (GUI), which allows the export of model logic and data in JSON format. The external solver, SAPHISOLVE, is included in the SAPHIRE software package.

When exporting the generic PWR models, 55 event tree models are split into 95 independent models. This allows each model to be solved separately, enabling parallel processing and significantly reducing computation time. The proposed solution was achieved using a Python script, with the pseudocode provided in Figure 2. As outlined, the models are quantified by calling necessary functions within the SAPHIRE software package, and both serial and parallel solution times are evaluated. As the number of available threads in the solution environment increases, the quantification time decreases considerably.

1. Import necessary libraries:
 - a. *os*: for file and directory operations
 - b. *threading*: for creating and managing threads
 - c. *ctypes*: to load and interact with the DLL
 - d. *time*: to measure solving times
2. Try to load the DLL:
 - a. If the DLL fails to load, print an error message and exit the script.
3. Define a function 'solve_json_file(input_file_path, output_directory)':
 - a. Generate the output file name by replacing the extension of the input file with '.JSCut'.
 - b. Measure the time taken to solve the JSON file using the SolveFromInput function from the DLL.
 - c. If there is an error during the solving process, print an error message.
4. Define a function 'solve_files_in_thread(files, input_directory, output_directory)':
 - a. For each file in the provided list of files, call the 'solve_json_file' function.
5. Define the 'main()' function:
 - a. Specify input and output directories.
 - b. List all JSON files in the input directory with the '.JSInp' extension.
 - c. Ensure the output directory exists; if it doesn't, create it.
6. Measure the time taken for serial processing:
 - a. For each JSON file in the list, call 'solve_json_file' to solve it serially.
 - b. Print the time taken for serial processing.
7. Measure the time taken for parallel processing:
 - a. Determine the number of CPU cores (threads).
 - b. Split the list of JSON files into chunks, one chunk per thread.
 - c. Create and start a thread for each chunk, calling 'solve_files_in_thread' in each thread.
 - d. Wait for all threads to complete.
 - e. Print the time taken for parallel processing.
8. Call the 'main()' function if the script is run directly.

Figure 2. Pseudocode for model quantification using SAPHIRE

This approach was compared with the standard SAPHIRE solution, and all cut sets and probabilities were identical. The solution results, along with all scripts used to run SAPHIRE, retrieve results, and conduct the analysis, are available in the repository [25]. For completeness, the results for the generic PWR model are presented in Table 1. The table also provides insight into what an actual PRA model looks like in terms of the number of sequences, cut sets, and event trees.

Table 1. Quantification results of generic PWR model.

#	Input-File	Number-of-Cut sets	Value-Cut sets	Number-of-Sequences
1	EQK-BIN1	610,016	2.085E-09	85
2	EQK-BIN2	811,575	2.430E-07	85
3	EQK-BIN3	802,392	2.336E-06	85
4	EQK-BIN4	598,505	2.857E-06	85
5	EQK-BIN5	440,041	2.348E-06	85

6	EQK-BIN6	177,330	6.005E-07	85
7	EQK-BIN7	2	9.623E-09	1
8	FLI-4160VACA	363,408	2.550E-09	29
9	FLI-4160VACB	364,430	2.564E-09	29
10	FLI-AFW-ROOM	126,120	2.109E-08	29
11	FLI-CCW-ROOM	283,639	2.941E-08	29
12	FLI-CCW-ROOMA	631,309	1.065E-09	29
13	FLI-CCW-ROOMB	636,421	1.066E-09	29
14	FLI-CVC-ROOM	277,526	3.958E-10	29
15	FLI-RHR-ROOM	36,008	1.071E-10	29
16	FLI-SWS-ROOM	190,025	2.997E-07	29
17	FLI-SWS-ROOMA	182,124	1.403E-08	29
18	FLI-SWS-ROOMB	188,786	1.410E-08	29
19	FRI-AB-AFWAB	420,246	1.244E-08	29
20	FRI-AB-CCWBC	528,190	7.673E-10	29
21	FRI-AB-LOOP	29,283	1.098E-08	33
22	FRI-AB-LOOP-DIVA	45,325	3.138E-06	33
23	FRI-AB-LOOP-DIVB	46,090	3.159E-06	33
24	FRI-AB-RHRA	647,063	2.114E-09	29
25	FRI-AB-SIS	659,428	5.416E-08	29
26	FRI-AB-SLOCA	14,257	5.500E-07	8
27	FRI-MCR	3,464	9.081E-06	6
28	FRI-SWS-BLD	71,923	9.331E-08	29
29	HCN-BIN1	1,703,431	4.868E-09	63
30	HCN-BIN2	1,064,448	2.181E-09	63
31	HCN-BIN3	475,235	9.346E-10	63
32	HCN-BIN4	230,212	4.738E-10	63
33	HWD-96MPH	2,558,791	2.264E-08	63
34	ISL-RHR-CL	217	3.063E-11	2
35	ISL-RHR-HL	3	2.063E-08	2
36	L4160ACA	160,390	2.207E-07	29
37	L4160ACB	162,204	2.220E-07	29
38	LLOCA	20,119	3.617E-07	3
39	LOCCW	778,360	8.245E-08	29
40	LODCA	156,714	4.249E-08	29
41	LODCB	160,549	4.271E-08	29
42	LOMFW	1,550,153	7.502E-08	18
43	LOOPGR	1,111,725	7.913E-07	33
44	LOOPPC	851,575	7.619E-08	33

45	LOOPSC	1,253,736	7.286E-07	33
46	LOOPWR	1,014,915	5.660E-07	33
47	LSSB	216,762	1.872E-07	16
48	MLOCA	67,620	9.333E-06	5
49	SGTR	1,039,329	2.669E-06	12
50	SLOCA	309,917	2.453E-05	8
51	TOR-BIN1	128,067	5.355E-12	63
52	TOR-BIN2	126,084	2.614E-11	63
53	TOR-BIN3	95,064	1.296E-10	63
54	TRANS	4,178,502	1.525E-07	29
55	XLOCA	1	0.000E+00	1
	TOTAL	28,559,059	6.502E-05	1965

1.2.2 Model Conversion from SAPHIRE to OpenPSA

The Model Exchange Framework (MEF) facilitates the transfer of models between different PRA tools. While the primary objective of this session is to establish a framework for exchanging models between different quantification engines, it is essential to note that MEF serves a broader purpose beyond enhancing the PRA tool quantification engine.

MEF plays a critical role in quality assurance by ensuring the portability of models across various tools. This capability becomes essential when switching between PRA tools, either by choice or as a requirement. For instance, if a PRA tool developer discontinues support, users may be unable to maintain their models without a reliable means of transfer.

Moreover, MEF is foundational in transitioning from desktop-based to web-based PRA tools, such as Open-PRA, or SAPHIRE. The web editor provided by Open-PRA allows users to create and quantify models using different tools—a feat that would not be achievable without an efficient MEF.

In the following sections, we summarize the current methods of MEF in Section 1.2.3 and introduce our proposed MEF in Section 1.2.4 with a demonstration.

1.2.3 Current Model Exchange Methodology

As discussed in the historical overview of PRA tools in the first milestone report, the NRC funded INL to develop a PRA tool, initially utilizing mainframe computer tools such as the Set Equation Transformation System (SETS) and the Top Event Matrices Analysis Code (TEMAC). Subsequently, personal computer (PC)-based software tools like IRRAS and the System Analysis and Risk Assessment (SARA) tools were developed to analyze and evaluate generic and PRA-related problems.

Recognizing the need for a centralized data repository, NRC initiated the development of the Models and Results Database (MAR-D) [21] to manage the transfer and storage of PRA data from mainframe to PC codes. MAR-D was vital in transitioning data between IRRAS, SARA, SETS, and FRANTIC software tools. It facilitated the loading, storing, and extracting of various PRA data elements, including event trees, sequences, fault trees, basic event failure rates, plant damage states, and component descriptions.

MAR-D's functionalities later became standard for SAPHIRE, enabling a smooth transition for the development team when major updates were implemented, as detailed in SAPHIRE Manual Volume 7 [26]. However, while MAR-D was efficient for transferring models within versions of SAPHIRE, it did not serve as a comprehensive model exchange framework.

CAFTA Version 11.0 enables the import of SAPHIRE MAR-D files. However, this process required significant manual effort and was unsuitable for large PRA models since CAFTA imports only logic files. Similarly, RiskA developers attempted to verify their engine against XFTA using Open-PSA MEF [27], but the methodology remains unavailable.

In 2013, an unsuccessful attempt was made to convert RiskSpectrum models to CAFTA [28], which shows the difficulty of efficient model exchange between RiskSpectrum and CAFTA. Additionally, an unpublished paper [29] claims that model conversion from RiskSpectrum to Open-PSA MEF and CAFTA to Open-PSA was accomplished in 2010. However, neither the methodology nor the results of these conversions are available for review.

A recent effort to exchange models between SAPHIRE and CAFTA was limited to fault tree model exchange and involved numerous manual operations [30].

Given the challenges faced in model exchange between various PRA tools, an efficient MEF solution remains critical. We propose an engine-level MEF framework in the following sections to facilitate smooth model exchange between different engines.

1.2.4 Method of Model Exchange Between PRA Tools

MEF is proposed as an engine-level framework that enables smooth model exchange between various quantification engines that are available to users.

The proposed MEF involves converting SAPHIRE models to Open-PSA MEF format. This conversion holds value as it allows real NPP PRA models to be available in Open-PSA MEF format, enabling PRA tool developers to test their tools using real-life and synthetically generated models. Additionally, this model conversion facilitates result verification. SAPHIRE, developed by the NRC, is expected to remain in use for the foreseeable future. A proficient MEF would enhance the model development capability of

Standardized Plant Analysis Risk (SPAR) [16] model developers and enable the SAPHIRE development team to improve SAPHISOLVE.

It is important to note that Open-PSA MEF was developed with contributions from various PRA tool developers across the industry and academia internationally. Conversion to Open-PSA MEF enhances the SCRAM engine and allows open-source developers to improve their engines by testing with real models.

A simple PRA model consists of one event tree linked to four fault trees, used for demonstration purposes, borrowed from a research paper [31].

Figure 3 depicts the event tree. The initiating event is the release of gas on an offshore platform. The gas detection system, isolation valve subsystems A and B, and the blowdown valve subsystem are subsequently identified as functional events. The outcomes determined by the endpoint of each event tree branch indicate different consequences following the initiating event.

Figure 3. Gas-leak event tree.

The fault trees provided in Figure 4 to Figure 7 are built to represent functional events described in the event tree.

Figure 4. Gas-detection system fault tree.

Figure 5. Isolation valve A fault tree.

Figure 6. Isolation valve B fault tree.

Figure 7. Blowdown valve fault tree.

The overall model exchange methodology is outlined in Figure 8. A model converter [25], written in Python, is employed to manage all necessary steps, including parsing the text-based file, converting it to the expected format, and saving the converted model in a text-based format. Both JSON and XML elements are defined as objects to facilitate easy manipulation.

Figure 8. Engine-Level Model Exchange Framework.

The initial step involves exporting the model from the engine. In our case, the exported model is a SAPH SOLVE JSON file. The second step entails parsing the model file and saving its elements as an object. Subsequently, the model is converted from one format to another, as demonstrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Demonstration of Engine-Level Model Exchange Framework.

Conversion from one format to another relies on understanding the formats. As depicted in Figure 9, fundamental objects are matched for different formats. Namely, initiating event information is available under the *header* element, *sysgatelists* element includes functional event information, *sequencelist* element includes sequence information, *faulttreelist* information includes fault tree logic, and *eventlist* element includes basic event failure data information.

As a follow-up, to verify the correctness of the conversion, the converted model is quantified using SCRAM, and the results for SAPH SOLVE, original SCRAM

quantification, and SCRAM converted model quantification are compared. Both the number of cut sets and the probability results are the same, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Demo model results comparison for SCRAM and SAPH SOLVE.

Engine	SCRAM		SAPH SOLVE	
Sequence	Probability	Number of cut sets	Probability	Number of cut sets
S1	1.00E+00	1	1.00E+00	1
S2	9.97563E-02	3	9.97563E-02	3
S3	9.97562E-02	3	9.97562E-02	3
S4	1.04637E-02	9	1.04637E-02	9
S5	9.97563E-02	3	9.97563E-02	3
S6	1.04637E-02	9	1.04637E-02	9
S7	1.04637E-02	9	1.04637E-02	9
S8	1.07637E-03	27	1.07637E-03	27
S9	5.71072E-02	4	5.71072E-02	4

The results of the generic PWR model conversion will be discussed in the final report of the project.

1.3 Conclusion and Alignment to Project Goals

The foundation for testing available quantification engines has been established. A model converter was proposed to create an actual PRA model in Open-PSA XML format, a crucial test case for quantification engine developers. While the model converter has been tested and is operational, some minor issues remain to be addressed due to the unique input requirements of each quantification engine.

Additionally, the model converter will be extended to convert the generic PWR models into other formats, such as FTREX's format, for completeness. Making an actual model accessible to everyone will not only enable performance measurement of the tools but also facilitate the verification of results. Furthermore, these efforts could improve modeling practices by reducing subjectivity in the process.

2 References

- [1] E. M. Aras, A. S. Farag, A. Earthperson, and M. A. Diaconeasa, "Benchmark Study of XFTA and SCRAM Fault Tree Solvers Using Synthetically Generated Fault Trees Models," in *Volume 9: Mechanics of Solids, Structures, and Fluids; Micro- and Nano-Systems Engineering and Packaging; Safety Engineering, Risk, and Reliability Analysis; Research Posters*, Columbus, Ohio, USA: American Society of Mechanical Engineers, Oct. 2022, p. V009T14A016. doi: 10.1115/IMECE2022-95783.
- [2] E. M. Aras, A. S. Farag, A. Earthperson, and M. A. Diaconeasa, "Methodology and Demonstration for Performance Analysis of a Probabilistic Risk Assessment Quantification Engine: SCRAM," in *18th International Probabilistic Safety Assessment and Analysis (PSA 2023)*, Knoxville, TN: American Nuclear Society, 2023, pp. 452–459.
- [3] E. M. Aras, A. S. Farag, A. Earthperson, and M. A. Diaconeasa, "Method of Developing a SCRAM Parallel Engine for Efficient Quantification of Probabilistic Risk Assessment Models," in *18th International Probabilistic Safety Assessment and Analysis (PSA 2023)*, Knoxville, TN: American Nuclear Society, 2023, pp. 134–140.
- [4] A. Earthperson, E. M. Aras, A. S. Farag, and M. A. Diaconeasa, "Introducing OpenPRA: A Web-Based Framework for Collaborative Probabilistic Risk Assessment," in *Proceedings of the ASME 2023*, New Orleans, Louisiana, USA, Oct. 2023.
- [5] A. Farag, S. Wood, A. Earthperson, E. Aras, J. Boyce, and M. Diaconeasa, "Evaluating PRA Tools for Accurate and Efficient Quantifications: A Follow-Up Benchmarking Study Including FTREX," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 573–582. doi: 10.13182/T130-43377.
- [6] E. Aras *et al.*, "Introducing OpenPRA's Quantification Engine: Exploring Capabilities, Recognizing Limitations, and Charting the Path to Enhancement," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 552–561. doi: 10.13182/T130-43362.
- [7] E. Aras, S. Wood, J. Boyce, A. Farag, and M. Diaconeasa, "Enhancing the SAPHIRE Solve Engine: Initial Progress and Efforts," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 542–551. doi: 10.13182/T130-43361.
- [8] S. Wood, J. Boyce, E. Aras, A. Farag, and M. Diaconeasa, "Advancing SAPHIRE: Transitioning from Legacy to State-of-Art Excellence," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 532–541. doi: 10.13182/T130-43357.
- [9] A. Earthperson, E. Aras, A. Farag, and M. Diaconeasa, "Towards a Deep-Learning based Heuristic for Optimal Variable Ordering in Binary Decision Diagrams to Support Fault Tree Analysis," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 400–409. doi: 10.13182/T130-43397.
- [10] E. M. Aras and M. A. Diaconeasa, "A Critical Look at the Need for Performing Multi-Hazard Probabilistic Risk Assessment for Nuclear Power Plants," *Eng*, vol. 2, pp. 454–467, 2021.

- [11] E. M. Aras, A. S. Amin Aly Farag, S. T. Wood, and J. T. Boyce, “Refining Processing Engines from SAPHIRE: Initialization of Fault Tree/Event Tree Solver,” Idaho National Laboratory (INL), Idaho Falls, ID (United States), INL/RPT-23-75066-Rev000, Oct. 2023. doi: 10.2172/2203095.
- [12] A. S. Farag, “Benchmarking Study of Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools Using Synthetically Generated Fault Tree Models: SAPHISOLVE, XFTA, and SCRAM,” North Carolina State University, Raleigh, North Carolina, 2023.
- [13] E. M. Aras, “Enhancement Methodology for Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools through Diagnostics, Optimization, and Parallel Computing,” Doctor of Philosophy, North Carolina State University, Raleigh, North Carolina, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://repository.lib.ncsu.edu/items/bb05f7f5-1cff-4beb-9312-331bc94b0b95>
- [14] E. M. Aras, A. S. Farag, A. Earthperson, and M. A. Diaconeasa, “Benchmark Study of XFTA and SCRAM Fault Tree Solvers Using Synthetically Generated Fault Trees Models,” in *Volume 9: Mechanics of Solids, Structures, and Fluids; Micro- and Nano-Systems Engineering and Packaging; Safety Engineering, Risk, and Reliability Analysis; Research Posters*, Columbus, Ohio, USA: American Society of Mechanical Engineers, Oct. 2022, p. V009T14A016. doi: 10.1115/IMECE2022-95783.
- [15] A. Rauzy, E. Châtelet, Y. Dutuit, and C. Bérenguer, “A practical comparison of methods to assess sum-of-products,” *Reliab. Eng. Syst. Saf.*, vol. 79, no. 1, pp. 33–42, Jan. 2003, doi: 10.1016/S0951-8320(02)00165-5.
- [16] R. R. Sherry, P. L. Appignani, and R. F. Buell, “The NRC’s SPAR Models: Current Status, Future Development, and Modeling Issues,” p. 11.
- [17] “SAPHIRE | Training Info.” Accessed: Aug. 09, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://saphire.inl.gov/#/>
- [18] A. Ayoub, W. Kröger, and D. Sornette, “Generic and adaptive probabilistic safety assessment models: Precursor analysis and multi-purpose utilization,” *Nucl. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 54, no. 8, pp. 2924–2932, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.net.2022.03.013.
- [19] E. Meléndez, “Standardized Probabilistic Safety Assessment Models: Status and First Results of SPAR-CSN Project,” *Uncertain. Quantif.*, 2021.
- [20] C. Smith, “Generic Pressurized Water Reactor Model for SAPHIRE,” INL/EXT-21-62553-Rev000, 1804754, Apr. 2021. doi: 10.2172/1804754.
- [21] K. A. Branham-Haar, R. A. Dinneen, K. D. Russell, and N. L. Skinner, “Models and Results Database (MAR-D), Version 4. 0,” NUREG/CR-5301, EGG--2627, 5299087, May 1992. doi: 10.2172/5299087.
- [22] E. M. Aras, A. S. A. A. Farag, S. T. Wood, and J. T. Boyce, “Refining Processing Engines from SAPHIRE,” Idaho National Laboratory, Idaho Falls, ID, INL/RPT-23-75066, Sep. 2023.
- [23] E. Steven and R. Antoine, Eds., “Open-PSA Model Exchange Format.” 2017.
- [24] E. Aras, A. Earthperson, and M. Diaconeasa, *Generic Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) SAPHISOLVE Model*. (Oct. 2024). Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13996960.
- [25] “Enhancement-of-PRA-Tools / Model-Exchange / Model-Converter · GitLab,” GitLab. Accessed: Apr. 19, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://gitlab.com/enhancement-of-pra-tools/model-exchange/model-converter>
- [26] “NUREG/CR-7039, Vol. 7, ‘Systems Analysis Programs for Hands-on Integrated Reliability Evaluations (SAPHIRE) Version 8 Volume 7: Data Loading.’”

- [27] J. Wang *et al.*, “Verification of RiskA calculation engine based on Open-PSA platform,” in *2013 International Conference on Quality, Reliability, Risk, Maintenance, and Safety Engineering (QR2MSE)*, Chengdu, China: IEEE, Jul. 2013, pp. 32–35. doi: 10.1109/QR2MSE.2013.6625529.
- [28] C. Rochon, C. Trull, D. Remlinger, and N. R. Labarge, “Conversion of Risk Model from RiskSpectrum to CAFTA,” p. 9.
- [29] S. Epstein, F. M. Reinhart, and A. Rauzy, “Validation Project for the Open-PSA Model Exchange using RiskSpectrum® and CAFTA®,” p. 5.
- [30] M. Hamza, A. Tezbasaran, E. Aras, A. S. Farag, and M. A. Diaconeasa, “Model Exchange Methodology Between Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools: SAPHIRE and CAFTA Case Study,” presented at the 18th International Probabilistic Safety Assessment and Analysis (PSA 2023), Knoxville, TN, Jul. 2023.
- [31] J. D. Andrews and S. J. Dunnett, “Event-tree analysis using binary decision diagrams,” *IEEE Trans. Reliab.*, vol. 49, no. 2, pp. 230–238, Jun. 2000, doi: 10.1109/24.877343.
- [32] A. Batikh and M. Diaconeasa, “OpenMHA: Open-Source Code for Creating Multi-Hazards Logic and Area PRA Models Considering Aging of SSCs,” in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 562–572. doi: 10.13182/T130-43381.
- [33] S. L. N. Dhulipala, A. Dahal, B. W. Spencer, A. Jain, A. S. Batikh, and M. A. Diaconeasa, “Preliminary Nuclear Containment Vessel Modeling for Multi-Hazard Probabilistic Risk Assessment under Seismic Hazards and Concrete Degradation,” presented at the 18th International Probabilistic Safety Assessment and Analysis (PSA 2023), Knoxville, TN, Jul. 2023.
- [34] A. S. Batikh, S. L. N. Dhulipala, B. W. Spencer, A. Dahal, and M. A. Diaconeasa, “Time-Dependent Fragility Curves for SSCs: Incorporating Seismic Aftershocks in Multi-Hazard PRA,” presented at the 18th International Probabilistic Safety Assessment and Analysis (PSA 2023), Knoxville, TN, Jul. 2023.
- [35] A. S. Batikh, S. L. N. Dhulipala, B. W. Spencer, A. Dahal, and M. A. Diaconeasa, “Integrating Seismic Fragility of ASR-Affected Nuclear Containment Vessel in a Level-II SPRA in Support of Multi-Hazard Risk Assessment,” presented at the 18th International Probabilistic Safety Assessment and Analysis (PSA 2023), Knoxville, TN, Jul. 2023.